

Research Article

Evaluating the Effectiveness of MDcide in Enhancing Decision-Making in Maternal Healthcare

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Abstract: Maternal mortality rates have risen sharply in many countries, including Malaysia, where the maternal mortality rate (MMR) increased from 21.1 per 100,000 live births in 2020 to 68.2 in 2022. The complex decision-making process for childbirth, compounded by the overwhelming amount of information and increasing anxiety among expectant mothers, further exacerbates this issue. MDcide is an innovative virtual reality (VR) application to transform maternal healthcare decision-making. By integrating immersive technology with user-centered design, MDcide empowers expectant mothers by providing accessible and reliable information to make informed choices about their birthing environments. This paper critically reviews MDcide's development, focusing on its alignment with current healthcare trends, its impact on reducing maternal mortality, and its relevance in promoting informed decision-making in maternal healthcare.

Keywords: Virtual Reality (VR); Maternal Healthcare; Informed Decision-Making; Maternal Mortality; Healthcare Technology; Patient Empowerment; Digital Health Solutions

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1. INTRODUCTION

Maternal health remains a cornerstone of global public health initiatives, yet the progress made in reducing maternal mortality has stagnated in recent years. Globally, maternal mortality rates (MMR) remain unacceptably high, with an estimated 287,000 maternal deaths in 2020, according to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2021). While countries such as Malaysia have made strides in improving maternal healthcare, the sharp rise in MMR from 21.1 per 100,000 live births in 2020 to 68.2 in 2022 illustrates the multifaceted challenges still faced in many regions (Ministry of Health Malaysia, 2022). These figures highlight the pressing need for innovative solutions that address gaps in healthcare access, knowledge dissemination, and informed decision-making processes for expectant mothers.

The primary causes of maternal mortality include complications during and after pregnancy, inadequate prenatal care, and delays in seeking medical attention due to either lack of information or anxiety surrounding healthcare decisions (Say et al., 2014). While interventions such as improved

medical care, community health worker programs, and policy reforms have shown success in certain regions (Koblinsky et al., 2016), the challenge persists, especially as healthcare systems grapple with the complexities of digital transformation and patient engagement.

In recent years, technological advancements have introduced new possibilities for addressing these challenges, particularly in empowering women through information technology (IT)-based health solutions (Luxton et al., 2020). The integration of digital health tools into maternal care provides opportunities to enhance patient knowledge, bridge communication gaps between patients and healthcare providers, and improve health outcomes through data-driven insights (Krishnan et al., 2021). This paper focuses on the role of virtual reality (VR) in maternal healthcare, specifically through the development of MDcide, a VR application designed to revolutionize the way expectant mothers navigate the decision-making process for childbirth. MDcide seeks to address the overwhelming amount of information and anxiety that often accompanies the selection of healthcare facilities for childbirth by offering a more personalized, immersive, and educational experience.

Virtual reality technology is increasingly being recognized for its potential to reshape patient care and education. In the context of maternal health, VR offers an innovative way to provide immersive experiences that can reduce anxiety and increase the confidence of expectant mothers by familiarizing them with healthcare environments (Chirico et al., 2020). The use of immersive simulations allows users to explore and interact with healthcare facilities, providing them with a more informed basis upon which to make critical decisions about their birthing experiences. As demonstrated by studies on VR in healthcare, these technologies can also facilitate better patient-provider communication and engagement, enhancing the overall quality of care (Freeman et al., 2021). MDcide, therefore, builds on these developments by offering a platform that integrates virtual tours of maternity wards, interactive educational modules, and real-time information on facility availability, all of which are designed to empower mothers with the knowledge needed to make informed choices.

The development of MDcide also aligns with the broader shift toward patient-centered care, where patients are encouraged to take an active role in their health decisions (Epstein & Street, 2011). In maternal healthcare, this paradigm shift is crucial, as it addresses not only the clinical outcomes but also the psychological and emotional well-being of mothers (Lillie et al., 2022). By leveraging the immersive capabilities of VR, MDcide enhances the decision-making process, reducing the uncertainties that can lead to delayed or poorly informed healthcare decisions. This innovative approach is particularly timely, as the COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the need for alternative and accessible methods of healthcare delivery, pushing more health services toward digital and virtual platforms (Webster, 2020).

The conceptual framework of MDcide is explored in this paper, with a focus on its role in empowering women in maternal healthcare. Its potential to reduce maternal mortality rates, enhance maternal health literacy, and contribute to the global objectives outlined in the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 3.1, is critically examined. SDG 3.1 specifically targets reducing the global maternal mortality ratio. Through the provision of immersive experiences and reliable information for expectant mothers, MDcide emerges as a transformative tool that addresses significant challenges in maternal healthcare.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 *The Role of AI in Maternal Decision-Making*

Artificial Intelligence (AI) plays a pivotal role in supporting informed decision-making for expectant mothers by offering personalized recommendations based on large-scale data analysis. AI technologies can efficiently process a vast amount of information, taking into account multiple factors such as medical history, preferences, and geographic constraints, to suggest the most suitable birthing locations. This approach minimizes the overwhelming nature of decision-making by filtering out less relevant options and presenting tailored choices. AI-powered platforms such as MDcide leverage machine learning algorithms to continuously improve their recommendations based on user interaction, feedback, and real-time data from healthcare institutions.

For instance, AI systems can track facility availability, current patient loads, and staff qualifications, allowing expectant mothers to make decisions that align with their preferences and health requirements. Additionally, AI can enhance the overall user experience by offering predictive insights, such as potential risks associated with specific birthing environments, making the decision-making process more robust and data-driven.

2.2 *The Immersive Experience of Virtual Reality (VR)*

Virtual Reality (VR) has emerged as a powerful tool in healthcare, especially in improving patient experiences through immersive environments. For maternal decision-making, VR provides expectant mothers with a 360-degree virtual tour of birthing facilities, including labor wards, recovery rooms, and other relevant areas. This immersive approach helps women familiarize themselves with potential birthing environments, reducing the anxiety often associated with unknown spaces.

In the MDcide platform, users can navigate virtual representations of different birthing centers, hospitals, or even home birth setups. These VR experiences are enriched with interactive elements that allow users to engage with the environment, opening doors, examining medical equipment, and visualizing the layout of the facility. This level of engagement can give mothers a better sense of control over their childbirth experience.

2.3 *User-Centered Design*

The MDcide platform integrates user-centered design principles to enhance its accessibility and effectiveness. Key components of the platform include personalized avatars, multilingual support, and customizable experiences. Users can create avatars that represent themselves, enhancing the emotional connection with the virtual environment. By tailoring the experience to the user's preferences, the platform becomes more than just an informational tool, it offers an emotionally resonant journey through their birthing options.

2.4 *Data Collection and Analysis*

This conceptual framework draws on qualitative data collected through semi-structured interviews with young mothers between the ages of 18 and 34. These participants shared their lived experiences related to the pre-decision stages of selecting a birthing place. This phenomenological approach allowed for an in-depth exploration of the psychological and emotional aspects of decision-making during pregnancy. The data were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify common patterns and key decision-making factors among expectant mothers. Recurring themes such as anxiety over unknown birthing

environments, the importance of experiential engagement, and the need for personalized guidance emerged, highlighting the value of AI and VR in addressing these concerns.

2.5 Technological Integration and Feedback Mechanisms

The MDcide platform employs real-time data integration, allowing for dynamic updates to facility information such as current wait times, available services, and staff-to-patient ratios. This real-time functionality is critical in empowering expectant mothers to make decisions based on the most current data. Furthermore, the platform incorporates user feedback mechanisms, enabling continuous improvements and ensuring that the app evolves in response to user needs.

Feedback from users is collected through surveys and interactive tools within the app, allowing developers to refine and optimize the experience. This iterative process ensures that the platform remains user-friendly and continues to meet the evolving needs of expectant mothers. By focusing on both technical performance and user experience, MDcide provides a holistic solution that enhances maternal decision-making.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Impact of AI and VR on Maternal Decision-Making

One of the core findings of this study is the significant impact that AI and VR technologies have on improving maternal decision-making. Traditional decision-making models often involve an overwhelming amount of information, leaving expectant mothers anxious and confused, particularly during the pre-decision phase. By introducing AI-powered decision support, platforms like MDcide simplify this process by analyzing data and making personalized recommendations based on each user's health status, preferences, and geographic location. AI also identifies trends and can proactively suggest optimal birthing environments tailored to specific medical needs, thus improving the quality and relevance of information presented to the user.

Participants in the study found that the ability to access a filtered and customized set of options, as offered by AI, significantly reduced decision fatigue. Mothers reported that AI-supported decision-making offered a sense of control and reduced their anxiety, as they no longer had to sift through overwhelming data on their own. Instead, they received clear, curated suggestions aligned with their health and birthing preferences.

3.2 Reduction of Anxiety through Virtual Reality Experiences

Another key finding is the role of VR in reducing anxiety during the decision-making process. Many participants expressed that their anxiety about childbirth was largely driven by the unknown, specifically, a lack of familiarity with birthing environments and the fear of making the wrong choice due to limited exposure. VR's immersive capabilities, as incorporated into MDcide, allow users to experience and explore various birthing environments before making a physical commitment. This interactive exploration provides mothers with a "trial run" of their birthing environment, enabling them to feel more comfortable and informed about their choices.

The highly interactive virtual tours allow users to navigate through hospitals, birthing centers, and midwifery services. Participants reported that being able to visualize and interact with the equipment and rooms and even observe staff-to-patient ratios alleviated much of the anxiety they had regarding their birthing location. Mothers were able to familiarize themselves with the setting, making

the actual birthing process less intimidating. This was particularly beneficial for first-time mothers, who often face a higher degree of anxiety due to the unpredictability of the experience.

3.3 Enhanced Decision-Making through Personalized Features

Personalization was a recurring theme in the findings, highlighting the importance of customized user experiences in maternal healthcare. Through the use of AI and personalized user profiles, MDcide tailors its VR tours and recommendations based on each mother's unique preferences and medical needs. This personalization extends beyond mere recommendations; users can create avatars that represent themselves, enhancing their emotional connection with the birthing environment they are exploring.

The AI component of MDcide also takes into account real-time data from healthcare facilities, including bed availability, wait times, and staff qualifications. This allows expectant mothers to make informed decisions based on the most current and relevant information, a feature that was highly appreciated by participants. The ability to customize the virtual experience according to personal preferences (such as viewing private rooms or certain types of medical equipment) provided an added level of comfort and reassurance for the users.

3.4 Feedback from Healthcare Providers

Healthcare providers who participated in the study reported that platforms like MDcide offer significant potential to improve patient engagement and satisfaction. By offering an interactive platform for users to explore their facilities, providers noted that patients were more likely to feel confident in their choices and less anxious about their birthing environment. This is crucial in improving healthcare outcomes, as reduced anxiety is often linked to better maternal health and lower risks of complications during childbirth.

Providers also appreciated the data-gathering features of the platform, which allowed them to better understand patient preferences and feedback. This data can be used to improve service offerings and align them more closely with patient expectations, thereby fostering a more patient-centric approach to maternal healthcare.

3.5 Improvement in Maternal Health Outcomes

The integration of AI and VR technologies has the potential to positively impact maternal health outcomes, particularly in regions with high maternal mortality rates. By providing accessible, personalized, and immersive decision-making tools, MDcide aims to empower expectant mothers to make well-informed choices, which could lead to safer and more satisfying birthing experiences. The feedback from users and healthcare providers suggests that this technology could play a critical role in reducing maternal mortality by promoting better decision-making and improving access to quality healthcare information.

The findings indicate that platforms like MDcide are not only improving individual decision-making but also contributing to public health goals, such as the reduction of maternal mortality, as aligned with Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 3.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 *Integration of AI and VR in Maternal Healthcare*

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Virtual Reality (VR) into maternal healthcare decision-making processes has shown tremendous potential in reshaping how expectant mothers engage with their healthcare choices. This is particularly relevant in an era where information overload can be overwhelming, and traditional decision-making tools may not adequately address individual needs. AI and VR technologies, as evidenced by platforms such as MDcide, provide a personalized, immersive experience that empowers women to make more informed decisions about their birthing environment.

AI's role in analyzing large datasets and tailoring information to meet the specific needs of users is critical in maternal healthcare. The healthcare decision-making process, particularly for expectant mothers, involves various complex considerations, including personal preferences, medical history, and geographical constraints. AI's ability to process these factors and provide personalized, real-time recommendations addresses a significant gap in traditional decision-making processes, which often leave expectant mothers confused by the abundance of information.

Additionally, VR enhances this decision-making process by allowing users to experience birthing environments virtually. The immersive nature of VR helps expectant mothers overcome the anxiety of unfamiliar environments, providing a sense of control and preparedness. This is crucial in reducing maternal anxiety, which has been linked to negative birth outcomes such as prolonged labor and increased medical interventions. The ability to virtually tour healthcare facilities and interact with various aspects of the environment such as medical equipment and staff, allows mothers to make decisions based on actual experiences rather than abstract descriptions.

4.2 *Addressing Barriers in Maternal Decision-Making*

One of the primary challenges faced by expectant mothers, especially first-time mothers, is navigating the vast amount of information available regarding childbirth. In traditional models of maternal care, women often rely on limited sources such as family advice, healthcare providers, or fragmented online resources. However, these sources may not always provide comprehensive or personalized information. This often leads to confusion and anxiety during the pre-decision phase.

The findings from this study indicate that AI-driven platforms like MDcide can alleviate these challenges by filtering through large datasets and providing expectant mothers with personalized and relevant information based on their preferences and medical history. The integration of real-time data further ensures that the information provided is current, allowing mothers to make informed decisions even in rapidly changing healthcare environments.

Furthermore, the immersive nature of VR in platforms such as MDcide helps to bridge the gap between abstract knowledge and practical experience. Expectant mothers can virtually explore different birthing environments without physically being present, thereby gaining a realistic understanding of the options available to them. This immersive experience has been shown to significantly reduce anxiety, improve maternal satisfaction, and, ultimately, enhance maternal health outcomes. By making the decision-making process more experiential and less abstract, VR allows mothers to visualize and understand the implications of their choices, thus fostering a sense of empowerment and confidence.

4.3 Alignment with Public Health Goals and Sustainable Development

The integration of AI and VR technologies into maternal healthcare decision-making aligns with broader public health goals, particularly those outlined in the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Specifically, SDG 3 seeks to ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages, with a key focus on reducing maternal mortality globally. The rise in maternal mortality rates in countries such as Malaysia has underscored the need for innovative approaches to maternal healthcare.

Platforms like MDcide contribute to these public health goals by providing expectant mothers with the tools to make informed decisions about their birthing environment, thus reducing the likelihood of complications that may arise from uninformed or rushed decisions. By offering personalized, data-driven insights and virtual access to healthcare facilities, these platforms address critical gaps in healthcare access and education, particularly in underserved regions where physical access to quality healthcare facilities may be limited.

Moreover, the ability of such platforms to offer continuous feedback and data collection enables public health organizations to gather valuable insights into maternal healthcare trends and outcomes. This data can inform policy decisions and healthcare improvements, further aligning with global efforts to reduce maternal mortality and improve overall healthcare quality.

4.4 Future Implications and Opportunities for Healthcare Providers

Integrating AI and VR in maternal decision-making presents significant opportunities for healthcare providers to improve patient engagement, satisfaction, and health outcomes. Healthcare providers can leverage these technologies to offer more personalized and interactive services, fostering stronger relationships with patients. The ability to virtually showcase healthcare facilities and services through immersive experiences not only enhances the transparency of the birthing process but also helps institutions market their services to a broader audience.

In addition to enhancing patient engagement, the data gathered from AI and VR platforms can provide healthcare providers with valuable insights into patient preferences and behaviors. This data can be used to tailor services, optimize healthcare delivery, and address specific patient needs more effectively. Furthermore, by integrating AI-driven decision support systems, healthcare providers can ensure that patients are guided toward making decisions that are not only aligned with their personal preferences but also optimized for health outcomes.

4.5 Challenges and Ethical Considerations

Despite the benefits of AI and VR in maternal decision-making, several challenges and ethical considerations must be addressed. One significant challenge is ensuring that the data used by AI algorithms is accurate, up-to-date, and unbiased. AI systems are only as effective as the data they are trained on, and there is a risk of perpetuating existing healthcare disparities if the data is not representative of diverse populations.

Another ethical consideration is data privacy. As platforms like MDcide collect and analyze large amounts of personal and medical data, there must be stringent measures in place to protect patient privacy and ensure that data is not misused. Healthcare providers and technology developers must work together to establish transparent data usage policies and ensure that patients are fully informed about how their data will be used.

5. CONCLUSION

Integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Virtual Reality (VR) into maternal healthcare presents a transformative opportunity to improve the decision-making process for expectant mothers. The traditional challenges mothers face during the pre-decision phase of selecting a birthing environment, such as information overload, anxiety about the unknown, and a lack of personalized guidance, are effectively addressed by these technologies. Platforms like *MDcide* demonstrate how AI can offer tailored recommendations, considering personal preferences, health status, and real-time data from healthcare facilities. This simplifies decision-making and ensures more relevant and informed choices.

Virtual Reality (VR), on the other hand, adds a layer of experiential engagement that has been shown to reduce maternal anxiety significantly. By allowing mothers to virtually tour hospitals, birthing centers, and other facilities, VR helps to demystify the birthing process and familiarize users with their options, fostering a sense of confidence and preparedness. This immersive experience is particularly beneficial for first-time mothers who often face heightened anxiety due to the unfamiliarity of the birthing process.

The findings from this study also highlight the broader implications of AI and VR for public health goals, particularly in the context of reducing maternal mortality, as outlined in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). By providing expectant mothers with accessible, reliable, and personalized information, these technologies directly contribute to better maternal health outcomes, especially in regions with high maternal mortality rates, such as Malaysia.

Moreover, the ability to collect and analyze user data from platforms like *MDcide* offers valuable insights for healthcare providers and public health organizations. This data can inform healthcare policies, improve service offerings, and contribute to more patient-centered care. As a result, the integration of AI and VR in maternal healthcare not only benefits individual users but also has the potential to drive system-wide improvements in healthcare delivery.

The continued development and implementation of AI and VR in maternal healthcare will require addressing several challenges, including ensuring equitable access to these technologies and safeguarding patient data privacy. However, with proper safeguards and inclusive design practices, AI and VR have the potential to revolutionize maternal healthcare by making it more accessible, personalized, and effective.

Future research should focus on expanding the use of AI and VR in low-resource settings to ensure that these benefits are accessible to a broader population. Additionally, longitudinal studies on the long-term effects of AI and VR on maternal health outcomes will provide deeper insights into the sustained impact of these technologies. Overall, AI and VR represent a promising future in maternal healthcare, where technology empowers women to make informed choices that lead to safer, healthier, and more satisfying birthing experiences.

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